

Modeling of Supply Chain Sustainability Enablers by Considering the Impact of COVID-19 on Developing Countries

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The increasing threat of pandemic is severe challenge for supply chain sustainability (SCs). The deadly virus devastated the global economy and disrupt manufacturing along with supply chain operations around the globe. We therefore made this attempt to identify the enablers of sustainability for supply chain (SC) practices from the context of developing economies. The interpretive structural modeling (ISM) employed for the partitioning of sustainability enablers by developing contextual relationship. At next stage, Matriced Impacts Crouses Multiplication Applique a un Classement (MICMAC) analysis used to classify enablers into different groups based on their driving and dependent power. The resultant hierarchical structure of ISM model shows that “Finance support (F3)” “Technological advancement (F2)” and “Develop sustainable procurement methods taking COVID-19 into consideration” are most influencing enablers of SCs to tackle the situation such as COVID-19. The findings of current study will provide guidelines to practitioners, policy makers, and government institutes to take initiatives for the practical implement of SCs by considering recommended factors.

Keywords: Supply chain sustainability; Emerging economies; Success factors; Economic disruption; CCOVID-19; ISM-MICMAC

1. Introduction

The increasing threat of COVID-19 which started to spread in 2019 from Wuhan city of China and later became the pandemic adversely affected SC operations [1, 2]. Current pandemic is by far the most destructive

disruption, It is reported that due to the pandemic more than 1 million people have lost their lives, 125 million workers lost their jobs only in Asia and Pacific, advanced economy whopped by 6 percent, and developing economies declined by 1 percent in 2020 [3]. The deadly virus is an alarming threat on SCs of emerging economies around the world. Furthermore, restrictions on travel by governments have severely affected the SC operations [1]. Approximately, 94% of fortune 1000 businesses have suffered the severity of supply chain operations due to coronavirus outbreak [4].

COVID-19 has slowdown the world's economies. The unprecedented health and economic shocks sparked by coronavirus also damaged the economy of Pakistan. The manufacturing sector in Pakistan contributes to GDP by 13-14 percent and consisted of 3 sub sectors: Small Scale Manufacturing (SSM), Large Scale Manufacturing (LSM) and Slaughtering. This sector is the main driver of economic development owing to its forward and backward connections to other economic sectors. The sector provides 16.1% employment opportunities. The only LSM shares 78 percent in manufacturing and contributes 9.5 percent to GDP. According to recent economic survey report of Pakistan, the growth of LSM is declined by -21.9 percent during the period of March 2020 due to Covid-19 outbreak and SC disruption of textile was the main reason behind such sharp declined [5].

The deadly virus brought unbearable crisis in the history of modern era. It has crashed the stock markets, collapsed the transportations system, led to delays in deliveries, and shortage of material [1]. In the light of such problems, the importance of sustainability became the major concern. Various academicians and experts have examined the influence of COVID-19 on supply chain operations [6]. Policy makers confronting variety of challenges to tackle SCs problems. The current pandemic crisis compelled enterprises to reconsider their global SCs approach to expedite their ability for the adaption of sustainability to address the situation same as COVID-19. Therefore, it is an urgent need to identify innovative methods which can help to implement SCs against global disruptions in the future [7].

In the past, researchers concentrated on cost-reduction and optimization strategies in supply chain management [8]. The latest pandemic has nevertheless changed the old SCs assumptions [4]. This pandemic not only has crashed old SC and operations strategies but also proven to be a challenging issue for policymakers. As deadly virus has variety of attributes therefore it will take long time to identify and eradicate it completely, most importantly this virus endangers the lives of millions of people [9]. Recently, SCs captured the attention of researcher community and practitioners. For instance, Bag, [10] analyzed operational procedure for the improvement of sustainability, de Sousa Jabbour, Jabbour [6] investigated the challenges in the context of SCs, Gupta, Kusi-Sarpong [11] highlighted the sustainability impact to strengthen the decision making power of policymakers, and Govindan, Mina [9] concluded that supply chain professionals need to invest more in robust transportation system, effective supply chain system, blockchain, automation and other emerging technologies. The required financial assistance for such kind of project from the government can help to upgrade the sustainability process to meet the modern demand.

The current scenario highlighted the severe effect of pandemic on SCs particularly from the aspect of emerging

economies. Therefore, author motivated that, it is deemed necessary to develop robust framework to investigate the enablers of SCs to tackle the situation same as pandemic. Current study will address the following question.

RQ 1: What are the enablers for the implementation of sustainability in supply chain to tackle the critical situation such as pandemic from the context of developing countries?

RQ 2: Identify the relationship between influencing enablers.

The COVID-19 pandemic is an utterly devastated disruption, which determines the sustainability of global economies. It is important to take steps for the protection of logistics capability, evaluation of structures and optimization where required, be responsive on the means of transportation, and ensure distribution networks remain operational during global disruptions. Hence, the strategic decisions concerning transportation systems, warehouse management, distribution of products, and packaging should be reevaluated to develop more effective strategies. Many medical manufacturing facilities have launched blockchain feasibility experiments in order to sustain flexibility and resiliency during the ongoing coronavirus pandemic [12]. The SC disruptions and transitions in the middle of the COVID-19 outbreak indicated urgent need for strategic and responsive measures to upgrade the supply networks and maintain efficiency via focusing on digital technology, real-time data processing, big data analytics, knowledge accessibility, and business constancy in multinational corporations [9].

Therefore, it is important to investigate sustainability drivers to achieve the fair level of competitiveness in developing economies before implementing sustainable practices and strategies. Thus, this research aims to contribute to literature by:

1. Selecting most relevant enablers of SCs sustainability from the past literature based on expert opinion.
2. Developing ISM-MICMAC model to allocate driving and dependent power to each enabler systematically.
3. Developing the hierarchical structure based on mutual relationships.
4. Providing recommendations to policy makers and practitioners.

The remainder of this study is structured as follow:

Section 1 consisted of background of COVID-19 and the significance of SCs. Section 2 highlighted studies on supply chain and the impact of COVID-19 on SC sector. Section 3 presented the models and methods for acquisition of data and analysis of data. Section 4 describes the results and significance of this study. Theoretical implementations are discussed in section 5. Section 6 provides the conclusion and shortcoming of current study.

2. Literature review

2.1 Studies on Supply chain and COVID-19

Supply chain sustainability described as, the alignment with triple bottom line i.e., economic, social, and environmental performance in the supply chain operations by considering the customer and stakeholders demand along with managing information, capital flow as well as enhancing the cooperation among firms [11]. The changes of global climatic conditions, inefficient use of resources, and economic recession are pursuing businesses to draw modern strategies for efficient operations[13]. The risk of the supply chain is often seen as potential threat in inbound supply operations that causes inability to satisfy consumer demand [14]. Vural [15] referenced that companies should consider possible environmental, social, and economic threats in their supply chains operations and formulate strategies accordingly. SCs significantly reduces negative operational, social, environmental, and economic impact and improve the performance of organizations [16]. Many businesses started to incorporate SCs to boost their corporate image and brand credibility [11]. However, several businesses in emerging economies do not have required resources to adapt sustainable practices [17]. The reason behind is that the concept of sustainability in SCs is still farfetched. The variety of SCs challenges are demanding attention at vast level in various developing countries to satisfy competitive business conditions. The pandemic brought huge disruption for the value chains of SC around the globe [9]. These substantial disruptions harmed the investments, sales revenues, procurement strategies, supply of products, brand images, stakeholders, consumers, and the overall supply chain efficiency [18]. This massive disruption occurred during the COVID-19 due to the inaccessibility of supply chain associated elements such as, production, procurement, and logistics [4]. Consequently, the management of SC system flopped during pandemic situation [19]. It is obvious that SC policies and procedures were designed for smooth business environment no to tackle situation same as pandemic. Hence, supply chain professionals and policy makers need to update SC policies and procedures to overcome such kind of situations. Aforementioned problems need to address in developing countries for sustainable and smooth supply chain operations to achieve sustainable performance by taking COVID-19 as an experience.

2.2 Drivers of supply chain sustainability

The smooth SC operations and production are inconvenience due to rapid changes in business environment, social and customer response [18]. The implementation of SCs highly dependent on a variety of important enablers which are associated with the organization. SCs enablers ensure efficient operations, economic development, managing of risks, satisfy the sustainability goals and help to adapt unpredictable conditions [20]. So far, the SCs failed to captured attention from the context of developing economies. Therefore, these important enablers need to be evaluated to address the impact of pandemics on SCs. Such drivers enable businesses to improve their overall performance. A literary survey was thus conducted by using given key points during the initialization process to accomplish this research: “Enablers of sustainability” “Sustainable implementation of supply chain operations” “Evaluation of sustainability drivers of COVID-19” “The effects

of pandemic on sustainability” and “The pandemic effect on economy”. Google academic and Scopus database were used for the exploration of literature. Finally, 9 SCs drivers were selected from existing literature and based on expert opinions. The detailed of CSFs for the sustainability is presented in table 1.

Table1. Literature table on CSFs of SCs

CSFs	References
F1 Develop sustainable procurement methods. taking COVID-19 into consideration	[6]
F2 Technological advancement	[21, 22]
F3 Finance support	[23]
F4 Reliability of delivery time	[24, 25]
F5 Use of data mining in supply chain	[26]
F6 Effective risk management disruption capacity	[6, 27]
F7 Develop a strong legislative framework to tackle COVID-19	[28]
F8 Customer support	[29, 30]
F9 Operations management	[10]

3. Materials and methods

This study evaluates enablers of SCs by employing two-steps methodology. At first stage the enablers of SCs were identified. At second stage, the contextual relationship was drawn based on ISM model.

3.1 Data collection

Previously, studies mainly focused on cost reduction strategies in supply chain or focused on smooth supply chain operations without considering the impact of global crisis same as pandemic. However, current study is empirical in nature and focused on SCs therefore team of expert selected to tackle this issue. Initially, 8 professionals contacted through phone calls. Finally, 6 experts agreed to participate in the study. The detail of experts is shown in table 2. The following questions were asked during the expert discussion.

Q1. What are the main influencing barriers of SCs?

Q2. What is relationship among these obstacles?

Table. 2 Details of Experts

Profession	Numbers	Experience
Professors	3	5+10+15
Supply chain Manager	2	10+10
Operations Manager	1	10

All responses of experts reported on the Self-Interaction Matrix (SSIM) based on 5 points Likert scale to develop contextual relationship among depended factors of ISM model. The ISM technique enables structural consistency and develops a multi-level framework. The steps of ISM are as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Step by step approach of ISM

3.2 ISM

This study provides a precise framework for the evaluation of drivers to promote a more efficient and intelligent SCs to address the situation same as COVID-19. ISM approach used to draw the hierarchical relationship between fuzzy drivers. ISM is an integrated Multiple Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) graph-based theory which was developed by Warfield and further illustrated by Malone (1975) via group judgment [31]. In this research, ISM Investigates the cause-and-effect relationship among different variables by

converting them into several levels. Thereafter, influencing drivers divided into four different categories based on their driving and dependence power by using the MICMAC approach. ISM used for this study due to following reasons.

1. ISM classifies a complex structure into different levels and builds an understandable diagram by considering the realistic knowledge and opinion of professionals.
2. ISM technique randomly prioritizes factors based on their importance without requiring any history.
3. The ISM process is an effective approach when multi-level research is needed, and the findings of the research cannot be estimated based on available data.

3.2.1 Self-structure interaction matrix (SSIM)

To develop SSIM the relationship between SCs enablers were drawn based on expert's opinion. Four symbols were used to interpret the relationships among two factors i, j as mentioned below. The SSIM is presented in table 3.

V: factor i is linked with j

A: factor j is linked with i

X: factor i and j both are linked

O: factor i and j are not linked with each other

Table 3 Self structure interaction matrix

SR NO.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
F1		V	V	A	A	A	V	V	A
F2			V	V	V	V	A	A	A
F3				A	V	V	V	A	V
F4					A	V	V	V	V
F5						V	V	O	V
F6							A	V	V
F7								V	A
F8									X
F9									

3.2.2 Initial reachability matrix (IRM)

The data seen in table 3 is converted into binary digits (i.e., 0 or 1) to establish an IRM by following up the conversion rule which is mentioned below. The IRM is shown in table 4

- If the entry (i, j) is represented by symbol "V" in the SSIM then this cell (i, j) entry converted into "1" and the cell (j, i) entry becomes "0" in the IRM.
- If the entry (i, j) is represented by symbol "A" in the SSIM then this cell (i, j) converted into "0" and the cell (j, i) entry transformed into "1" in the IRM.

- If the entry (i, j) is presented by symbol “X” in the SSIM then cell (i, j) converted into “1” and the cell (j, i) also transformed into “1” in the IRM.
- If the cell (i, j) is represented by symbol “O” in the SSIM then cell (i, j) converted into “0” and the cell (j, i) also transformed into “0” in the IRM.

Table 4 Initial reachability matrix

SR NO.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
F1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0
F2	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
F3	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1
F4	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
F5	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
F6	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1
F7	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0
F8	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
F9	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1

3.2.3 Final reachability matrix (FRM)

The FRM is obtained by incorporating the transitivity rule on IRM. The fundamental assumption of ISM states that if attribute 1 is linked to 2 and attribute 2 to 3 criterion then 1 is inevitably connected to criterion 3. The FRM is presented in table 5.

Table 5 Final reachability matrix

SR NO.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Dri.
F1	1	1	1	1*	1*	1*	1	1	0	8
F2	0	1	1	1	1	1	1*	0	1*	7
F3	1*	0	1	1*	1	1	1	0	1	7
F4	1	1*	1	1	1*	1	1	1	1	9
F5	1	1*	1*	1	1	1	1	1*	1	9
F6	1	1*	1*	1*	1*	1	1*	1	1	9
F7	1*	1	1*	1*	1*	1	1	1	1*	9
F8	1*	1	1	1*	1*	1*	1*	1	1	9
F9	1	1	1*	1*	1*	1*	1	1	1	9
Dep.	8	8	9	9	9	9	9	7	8	76

3.2.4 Level of partition

The final reachability matrix used to extract reachability and antecedent set. The reachability set is consisted of value 1 in each row, antecedent set is consisted of value 1 in each column, and the intersection set is

developed by matching the values of antecedent and reachability set. Consequently, the different factors assigned to different levels. All levels are presented in table 6.

Table 6 Level of partition

Sr. no	Reachability set	Antecedent set	Intersection set	Levels
Interaction 1				
1	1,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8	1,3,4,5,6,7,8	
2	1,2,4,5,6,7,8,9	2,3,4,5,6,7,9	2,4,5,6,7,9	
3	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,3,4,5,6,7,9	1,3,4,5,6,7,9	
4	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	
5	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	
6	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	
7	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	
8	1,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,4,5,6,7,8,9	
9	2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	
Interactions 2				
Sr. no	Reachability set	Antecedent set	Intersection	Levels
F1	1,3	1,2,3	1,3	2
F2	2	2,3	2	3
F3	3	3,	3	4
F4	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1
F5	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1
F6	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1
F7	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1
F8	1,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,4,5,6,7,8,9	1
F9	2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9	1

3.2.5 ISM model

Relationship among influencing enablers of ISM model is presented in Figure 2. The contextual relationship is drawn by considering the driving and dependence power of each enablers separately from FRM.

Figure 2. ISM structural model

4. Results and discussion

The present paper has outlined the enablers that would be more effective in designing strategies to strengthen SCs in the emerging economies by considering the situation such as COVID-19. As shown in Figure 2, “Financial support (F3)” is the foundation of ISM model and existed at level 4. It is most important enabler among all others. Respectively, “Technological advancement (F2)” is significant factor after financial support and exist at level 3 triggered from “Financial support (F3)” of level 4th. According to ISM model, both have direct relationship and influencing to each other. Finally, “Develop sustainable procurement methods taking COVID-19 into consideration (F1)” is triggered by “Technological advancement (F2)” of level 3 and result

shows that it has significant value in the hierarchical structure of ISM model due to direct relationship with the factors of 4th and 3rd level. The level 1 is discarded from study due to insignificance of their characteristics in our model, further detail of each level is described below.

4.1 Financial support (F3)

The financial support (F3) directly influences on the factors of level 3 and level 2. During the outbreak of COVID-19 most of the businesses faced economic recession in developing economies, so it would be impossible for companies to regain their losses without the compensation of financial institution such as government, banks, and supply chain partners. Therefore, it is important that financial assistance should provide by financial institutions in the form of bonuses, subsidization, and loans by considering the ratio of losses. Saeed and Kersten [32] aligned with our study that financial support can bring fruitful outcome in the SCs.

4.1.1 Technological advancement (F2)

Financial support and Technological advancement (F2) influencing each other because financial assistance will enable businesses to implement blockchain technology and expand the use of robotics and automation in production and logistics services. Saberi, Kouhizadeh [33] also proposed that technological advancement can revolutionize and improve SCs. The COVID-19 pandemic has shaken things for emerging economies. Therefore, it is important to embrace digital and advanced technology to reduce labor dependence and ensure safe, fast, online, and contactless transactions to tackle the situation same as pandemic.

4.1.2 Develop sustainable procurement methods taking COVID-19 into consideration (F1)

Develop sustainable procurement methods taking COVID-19 into consideration (F1) is existed at level 2. The procurement solutions to understand the situation of COVID-19 might be a key problem for all forms of SCs. The spreading of Covid-19 from China which is the world leader in the context of supply to several industries is challenging professionals to rethink about supply chain strategies. It is, therefore, imperative for all developing economies to draw sustainable procurement strategies to avoid supply disruption.

5. MICMAC analysis

MICMAC ('Matrice d'impact croise-multiplication applique an classment' or cross-impact matrix multiplication) analysis the graph-based model has four quadrant and classify each enabler in different quadrant based on their dependence and driving power as shown in figure 3 [34].

The four main quadrant of MICMAC are:

(1) autonomous category; (2) dependent category; (3) linkage category; and (4) driving category.

Autonomous category: Autonomous quadrant has weak dependence and driving power. Quadrant has failed to achieve any enabler due to strong dependence and driving power in a system.

Dependent category: This quadrant has strong dependence power and low driving power. None of any driver appears in this quadrant due to high dependence power and strong driving power.

Linkage category: All nine SCs enablers existed in the linkage category based on their strong dependence and driving power. Its means that any impact on these variables will affect to whole system.

Driving category: This quadrant has weak dependence and strong driving power. None of any factor emerge in this category due to strong dependence power.

Figure 3. MICMAC analysis for SCs

5.1 Theoretical implementation of study

The key drivers that enterprises must have to concentrate are "Financial support" "Technological advancement" and "Development of sustainable procurement methods taking COVID 19 into consideration" across the supply chain to enhance flexibility, agility, sustainability, and risk disruption. The results of this study could be use as a benchmark by managerial practitioners and policy makers to boost organizational success by adopting sustainability in developing markets during the situation same as COVID-19. Managers and policymakers need to ensure the safety and health protocols at working place during any kind of contagious diseases to avoid the disruption of supply. The proposed attempt is a step into the direction of SCs. It will provide clear understanding and inter-relationship of different enablers of SCs.

The current work will provide guidelines to policy makers to implement findings in a practical manner for the implementation of SCs procedures in a manufacturing sector.

6. Conclusion

COVID-19 is an unexpected and unprecedented phenomenon which affected SCs worldwide. This is a new challenge for policy makers to ensure SCs by taking COVID-19 situation into experience. To address this question, the enablers for the adoption and implementation of sustainability are properly delineated, evaluated and rated to provide detailed insight. Nine enablers of SCs were identified from past literature with the opinion of experts. The interpretive structural modeling employed to develop relationship among fuzzy factors.

Thereafter, the hierarchical structure model developed by assigning the links among fuzzy factors based on their contextual relationship. The MICMAC analysis then classified these factors in different quadrants based on their driving and dependence power and provides clear understanding of SCs enablers. The results show that “Finance support (F3)” “Technological advancement (F2)” and “Develop sustainable procurement methods taking COVID-19 into consideration (F1)” are most significant factors of SCs. It is indicated that most businesses faced economic crisis due to severe pandemic situation in developing countries thus financial aid by financial institutions can help businesses to recover their loss and will encourage them to acquire modern technology. Respectively, the procurement teams should evaluate the risk of delivery by suppliers’ side and develop sustainable procurement methods by taking COVID-19 into consideration. It is important for all organization to work with collaboration for the implementation of SCs. The presented study could be used to evaluate and address the situations to ensure the sustainability of business performance in the scope of COVID-19.

Despite it, the current research provides valuable insight for SCs but still it has some limitations. In this research we considered only 9 factors from previous literature the size of data can be increased further. The variation of results can be expected by using different methodologies such as AHP, PLS(SEM) and fuzzy topsis. The different opinions by different group of experts can influenced the current results.

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